

TRIPARTITE KEY AGREEMENT PROTOCOL USING TRIPLE DECOMPOSITION SEARCH PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT

A Key Agreement Protocol is a tool by which two parties can share a common key for their subsequent communication .Many cryptographic protocols are based on the hardness of Integer Factorization and Discrete Logarithm Problem. Very few Protocols are based on search problems in non – abelian groups. In this paper we present a Tripartite Key Agreement Protocol Using Triple Decomposition Search Problem using which three parties may agree on a common shared key in two rounds. We have chosen Discrete Heisenberg group and three cyclic sub groups as our platform to apply the above protocol.

KEY WORDS

Search Problems, Non –abelian group, Key Agreement Protocol, Triple Decomposition Search Problem ,Discrete Heisenberg Group.

1. INTRODUCTION

A key agreement is a protocol by which two parties, commonly named Alice and Bob, agree on a secret key to use in their subsequent private communication. Key exchange is an essential part of public key system. The first key exchange scheme was introduced by Diffie and Hellman in 1976, and independently by Merkle in 1978. So far, several key exchange protocols have been developed using the concept of combinatorial group theory, namely the Word Problem, Conjugacy Search Problem, Decomposition Problem, Triple Decomposition Problem Membership Search Problem and so on. In this paper we have proposed a Tripartite Key Agreement Protocol (KAP) using triple Decomposition Search Problem and applied it in the discrete Heisenberg group.

Some of the tripartite protocols proposed earlier are as follows:., Yesem Kurt[9] proposed a key exchange protocol using triple decomposition problem on Braid groups for two parties. A.Joux [1] proposed a One Round Protocol for tripartite Diffie-Hellman. Zhaohui Cheng, Luminita Vasiliu and Richard Comley [11] proposed Pairing- Based One –Round Tripartite Key Agreement Protocol. Atul Chaturvedi, Varun Shukla [3] proposed a tripartite key agreement protocol using conjugacy problem in Braid groups. Hung-Yu Chien* and Ru-Yu Lin [4] proposed “ An

Improved Tripartite Authenticated Key Agreement Protocol Based on Weil Pairing” using Elliptic Curve.

The paper is organised in the following manner. In section 2 , we have discussed the basic concepts of Discrete Heisenberg Group ; Section 3 introduces the triple decomposition problem and presents the protocol; In section 4 we have discussed the implementation of tripartite KAP using triple decomposition problem in the discrete Heisenberg group; In Section 5 , we have presented the security analysis of the proposed protocol . In Section 6, we have introduced some Encryption Schemes and Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. INTRODUCTION TO DISCRETE HEISENBERG GROUP

The Discrete Heisenberg group \mathcal{H} may be described as the set Z_p^3 of all integer triples endowed with the following multiplication,

where p is a prime : $(x, y, z) \cdot (u, v, w) = (x + u + yw, y + v, z + w) \text{ mod } p$

2.1. Some Computational Facts About \mathcal{H} .

The following computational facts about \mathcal{H} can be easily derived from the definition of multiplication given above.

2.1.1. Proposition.

Let x, y, z, u, v, w, n be any integers. Then the multiplication in \mathcal{H} satisfies the following equations:

- (a) $(x, y, z)^{-1} = (-x + yz, -y, -z) \text{ mod } p$
- (b) $(x, y, z) \cdot (u, v, w) \cdot (x, y, z)^{-1} = (u + yw - zv, v, w) \text{ mod } p$
- (c) $[(x, y, z), (u, v, w)] = (yw - zv, 0, 0) \text{ mod } p$
- (d) In particular, $[(0, 1, 0), (0, 0, 1)] = (1, 0, 0)$.
- (e) (i) $(x, 0, 0) \cdot (0, y, z) = (x, y, z) \text{ mod } p$
 (ii) $(0, y, 0) \cdot (0, 0, z) = (yz, y, z) \text{ mod } p$
 (iii) $(0, 0, z) \cdot (0, y, 0) = (0, y, z) \text{ mod } p$
- (f) (i) $(1, 0, 0)^n = (n, 0, 0) \text{ mod } p$
 (ii) $(0, 1, 0)^n = (0, n, 0) \text{ mod } p$
 (iii) $(0, 0, 1)^n = (0, 0, n) \text{ mod } p$

2.2. Centre $Z[\mathcal{H}]$:

Centre of \mathcal{H} coincides with $Z \times 0 \times 0$ where $\mathcal{H} = Z_p^3$.
 $[H, H] = Z [H]$.

2.3. Generators of \mathcal{H} :

Formulae (d)-(f) show that $(0, 1, 0)$ and $(0, 0, 1)$ generate H. Specifically,

$(x, y, z) = [(0, 1, 0), (0, 0, 1)]^x \cdot (0, 0, 1)^z \cdot (0, 1, 0)^y$, for all (x, y, z) in \mathcal{H} .

For the next result, we use the non-standard notation $n^{(2)}$ to stand for $n(n-1)/2$, for any integer ‘n’.

2.4. Proposition.

For any $(x, y, z) \in \mathcal{H}$ and any $n \in Z$, we have

$(x, y, z)^n = (nx + n^{(2)}yz, ny, nz)$.

Presentation of \mathcal{H} :

2.5. Proposition.

\mathcal{H} may be presented as

$\langle \sigma, \tau : [\sigma, \tau] = 1 = [\sigma, \tau] \rangle$, with σ (resp., τ) corresponding to the generator $(0, 1, 0)$ (resp. $(0, 0, 1)$).

We state the following results without proof:

2.6. Result 1:

Let L be any group, and let σ and τ be any elements of L satisfying the two relations given in Proposition 2.5. Then, there is a unique homomorphism $h : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow L$ such that $h(0, 1, 0) = \sigma$ and $h(0, 0, 1) = \tau$.

2.7. Result 2:

Let σ and τ be any elements of \mathcal{H} . There exists a unique endomorphism h of \mathcal{H} such that $h(0, 1, 0) = \sigma$ and $h(0, 0, 1) = \tau$. Let ϕ be an endomorphism from \mathcal{H} to \mathcal{H} and let $\phi(0, 1, 0) = (a, b, c)$, $\phi(0, 0, 1) = (d, e, f)$ and $\phi(x, y, z) = (x, y, z)$.

3 . THE TRIPLE DECOMPOSITION PROBLEM

In order to describe the system in a more general setting we assume the underlying structure is a non-commutative group.

Definition: A non – commutative group G is an algebraic structure with a binary operation \cdot and whose elements satisfy the following axioms.

- (i) For a, b in G , $a \cdot b$ is in G (Closure property)
- (ii) For a, b, c in G , $a \cdot (b \cdot c) = (a \cdot b) \cdot c$ (Associative property)
- (iii) There exists an element e in G such that for all a in G , $a \cdot e = e \cdot a = a$ (Existence of identity)
- (iv) For all a in G there exists an element a^{-1} in G such that $a \cdot a^{-1} = a^{-1} \cdot a = e$ (Existence of inverse)
- (v) In general $a \cdot b \neq b \cdot a$ (non –commutativity)

Definition : For $g \in G$, let $C (g) = \{ h \in G / gh = hg \}$. $C(g)$ is called the **centralizer** of g in G .

For a subset $H = \{ g_1, g_2, g_3, \dots, g_k \}$ of G , define $C (H) = C (g_1, g_2, \dots, g_k)$ to be the set of elements in G that commute with all g_i , $i=1, 2, \dots, k$. In other words, $C (H) = C (g_1) \cap C (g_2) \cap \dots \cap C (g_k)$.

The Protocol:

The system requires a non –commutative group G with two sets of subgroups S_{x1} & S_{x2} and S_{y1} & S_{y2} that are finitely generated and the users publishes the generators of the sub groups.

The elements of the above subgroups satisfy the condition called commutativity condition, viz., the elements of the above subsets commute with each other.

The protocol goes as follows:

Alice picks two elements $x_1, x_2 \in G$, chooses subsets S_{x_1} and S_{x_2} which are subsets of centralizers of x_1 and x_2 respectively. Alice publishes S_{x_1} and S_{x_2}

Bob picks two elements $y_1, y_2 \in G$, chooses subsets S_{y_1} and S_{y_2} which are subsets of centralizers of y_1 and y_2 respectively. Bob publishes S_{y_1} and S_{y_2}

Alice chooses random elements $a_1 \in G, a_2 \in S_{y_1}, a_3 \in S_{y_2}$.
 (a_1, a_2, a_3) is her private key.

She sends Bob her public key (u, v, w) where $u = a_1 x_1, v = x_1^{-1} a_2 x_2, w = x_2^{-1} a_3$
 Bob chooses random elements $b_1 \in S_{x_1}, b_2 \in S_{x_2}$ and $b_3 \in G$
 (b_1, b_2, b_3) is his private key

He sends Alice his public key (p, q, r) where $p = b_1 y_1, q = y_1^{-1} b_2 y_2, r = y_2^{-1} b_3$
 Alice computes $a_1 p a_2 q a_3 r = a_1 b_1 a_2 b_2 a_3 b_3 = K_A$
 Bob computes $u b_1 v b_2 w b_3 = a_1 b_1 a_2 b_2 a_3 b_3 = K_B$
 $K_A = K_B = K$ is their shared secret key

The security of the system depends on solving the equations

$$u = a_1 x_1 \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$v = x_1^{-1} a_2 x_2 \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$w = x_2^{-1} a_3 \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

to get the private key of Alice.

Solving equation (2), viz., decomposing v as three elements x_1^{-1}, a_2 and x_2 is known as the triple decomposition problem. In order to apply the triple decomposition, the platform group must

satisfy the following properties:

- P1) The group should be a non commutative group of exponential growth
- P2) It should be computationally easy to perform group operations (multiplication and inversion)
- P3) It should be computationally easy to generate pairs $(a, \{a_1, \dots, a_k\})$ such that $a a_i = a_i a$ for $i = 1 \dots k$
- P4) For a generic set $\{g_1, \dots, g_k\}$ of elements of the group it should be difficult to compute $C(g_1, \dots, g_k) = C(g_1) C(g_2) \dots C(g_k)$
- P5) Even if $H_1 = C(g_1, \dots, g_k)$ and $H_2 = C(g_1^{-1}, \dots, g_k^{-1})$ are computed it should be hard to find $x \in H_1$ and $y \in H_2$ and $a \in H$ where H is some fixed subgroup given by its generating set such that $x a y = v$ for any $v \in \mathcal{H}$.

4. IMPLEMENTATION OF TRIPLE DECOMPOSITION IN DISCRETE HEISENBERG GROUP

HEISENBERG GROUP:

Three parties A, B and C agree on a finite non-abelian group (Discrete Heisenberg group)

$G : \mathcal{H} = Z_p^3$ where p is sufficiently large prime.

They agree on three cyclic subgroups $G_1 = \langle e, g_1, g_2 \rangle$ such that $g_1 g_2 = g_2 g_1$,

$G_2 = \langle e, h_1, h_2 \rangle$ such that $h_1 h_2 = h_2 h_1$, and $G_3 = \langle e, k_1, k_2 \rangle$ such that $k_1 k_2 = k_2 k_1$.

Also the generators of G_1 do not commute with the generators of G_2 and G_3 and generators of G_2 do not commute with the generators of G_3 .

The protocol runs as follows

A chooses elements $a_1 \in G_1, a_2, x_1 \in G_2$ and $a_3, x_2 \in G_3$ and computes $u_{11} = a_1 x_1, v_{11} = x_1^{-1} a_2 x_2$
 $w_{11} = x_2^{-1} a_3$

B chooses elements $b_1 \in G_1, b_2, x_1 \in G_2$ and $b_3, x_2 \in G_3$ and computes $p_{11} = b_1 y_1, q_{11} = y_1^{-1} b_2 y_2$,
 $w_{11} = y_2^{-1} b_3$

C chooses elements $c_1 \in G_1, c_2, z_1 \in G_2$ and $c_3, z_2 \in G_3$ and computes $l_{11} = c_1 z_1, m_{11} = z_1^{-1} c_2 z_2$,
 $w_{11} = z_2^{-1} c_3$

I Round :

A sends (u_{11}, v_{11}, w_{11}) to B

B sends (p_{11}, q_{11}, r_{11}) to C

C sends (l_{11}, m_{11}, n_{11}) to A

A computes $u_{12} = a_1 l_{11}, v_{12} = a_2 m_{11}, w_{12} = a_3 n_{11}$

B computes $p_{12} = b_1 u_{11}, q_{12} = b_2 v_{11}, r_{12} = b_3 w_{11}$

C computes $l_{12} = c_1 p_{11}, m_{12} = c_2 q_{11}, n_{12} = c_3 r_{11}$

II Round :

A sends (u_{12}, v_{12}, w_{12}) to B

B sends (p_{12}, q_{12}, r_{12}) to C

C sends (l_{12}, m_{12}, n_{12}) to A

A computes $K_A = a_1 l_{12} a_2 m_{12} a_3 n_{12}$

B computes $K_B = b_1 u_{12} b_2 v_{12} b_3 w_{12}$

C computes $K_C = c_1 p_{12} c_2 q_{12} c_3 r_{12}$

$K = K_A = K_B = K_C$ is their common shared key

CORRECTNESS :

$K_A = a_1 c_1 b_1 y_1 a_2 c_2 y_1^{-1} b_2 y_2 a_3 c_3 y_2^{-1} b_3 = a_1 c_1 b_1 a_2 c_2 b_2 a_3 c_3 b_3$

$K_B = b_1 a_1 c_1 z_1 b_2 a_2 z_1^{-1} c_2 z_2 b_3 a_3 z_2^{-1} c_3 = b_1 a_1 c_1 b_2 a_2 c_2 b_3 a_3 c_3$

$K_C = c_1 b_1 a_1 x_1 c_2 b_2 x_1^{-1} a_2 x_2 c_3 b_3 x_2^{-1} a_3 = c_1 b_1 a_1 c_2 b_2 a_2 c_3 b_3 a_3$

Since a_1, b_1, c_1 commute a_2, b_2, c_2 commute and a_3, b_3, c_3 commute, $K = a_1 b_1 c_1 a_2 b_2 c_2 a_3 b_3 c_3$ is their common shared key.

5. ENCRYPTION AND DECRYPTION:

The three entities A, B and C may use their common key for encrypting and decrypting the messages.

Encryption Scheme1:

Encryption:

If suppose A wants to send a message 'm' to B or C, he computes $E = K m K^{-1}$ and sends E to B or C

Decryption:

Since B and C know the value of K , they decrypt as follows, $D = K^{-1} E K = K^{-1} K m K^{-1} K = m$

Encryption Scheme 2 :

Apart from having the common key, they may agree on an endomorphism $\mathcal{H} : \mathcal{H}$ and they may use the twisted conjugacy search problem for encryption and decryption .

Encryption:

A computes $E = K m (K^{-1})$ and sends to B or C

Decryption:

B and C have the value of K ,they decrypt $D = K^{-1} E (K) = K K^{-1} m (K^{-1}) (K) = m$

Encryption Scheme 3:

A encrypt the message m by finding $E = Km$ and sends to B or C

B and C have the key K, they decrypt $D = K^{-1} E = K^{-1} K m = m$

6. SECURITY ANALYSIS:

An adversary looking for A's public key in first round ,needs to solve the following;

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= a_1 x_1 \\
 \text{Let } u &= (u_1, u_2, u_3) \\
 a_1 &= (a, b, c), \quad x_1 = (x, y, z) \\
 u &= (a_1, b_1, c_1) \cdot (x_1, y_1, z_1) = (a+x+bz, b+y, c+z) \\
 u_1 &= a+x+bz, \quad u_2 = b+y, \quad u_3 = c+z \dots\dots\dots(1)
 \end{aligned}$$

If he wants to resolve a_1 or x_1 he has to solve the system of equations in (1)

Similarly he has to solve another set of equations of the same type as in (1) to recover a_3 or x_2 from w.

If he wants to recover a_2 or x_2 , he has to solve the following equations

$$v = x_1^{-1} a_2 x_2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } v &= (v_1, v_2, v_3), x_1 = (x, y, z), x_2 = (x^1, y^1, z^1), a_2 = (a^1, b^1, c^1) \\ (v_1, v_2, v_3) &= (x, y, z)^{-1} \cdot (a^1, b^1, c^1) \cdot (x^1, y^1, z^1) \\ &= (-y + xz + a^1 + x^1 + b^1 z^1 - yc^1 - yz^1 - y(c^1 + z^1), -y + b^1 + y^1, -z + c^1 + z^1) \end{aligned}$$

He has to solve the following system of equations,

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= -y + xz + a^1 + x^1 + b^1 z^1 - yc^1 - yz^1 - y(c^1 + z^1) \\ v_2 &= -y + b^1 + y^1 \\ v_3 &= -z + c^1 + z^1 \end{aligned}$$

Solving for v is known as triple decomposition problem.

7. CONCLUSION.

In this paper we have proposed a tripartite Key agreement protocol using triple decomposition problem by choosing Discrete Heisenberg group as the platform group. Solving for the public keys in the first round itself is sufficiently complicated ; if suppose an adversary happened to know the communications between the entities in the second round , he needs to solve a more complicated system of equations than the one in the first round. So this protocol would present a secure key exchange between three entities.

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Short Biography

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2. Dr. K. Sankarasubramanian, received his B.Sc. degree and M.Sc. (Mathematics) degree from Bangalore University and he got his doctorate from Sri Sathya Sai Institute for Higher Learning. The thesis title is ‘Flows of suspensions of particles and stratified fluids’. Two candidates have received Ph.D. Degree under his Guidance from Mother Theresa University. He has published 15 research papers in various National and International Journals in the field of Fluid Dynamics, Image Processing, Software error detection and Cryptography. His current area of research interest includes “Non-abelian group-based cryptography”; he has a very vast teaching experience of 33 years.

